



The full RADX Tribal Data Repository team includes Stanford University, as the prime awardee and project administrator and Native BioData Consortium as the project leader. The project will be guided by NativeBio consortium members from the University of Wisconsin-Madison, The Ohio State University, the University of California-Santa Cruz, Arizona State University, and the University of Washington-Seattle.

Stanford and NativeBio have worked together for more than 10 years. “Stanford believed in our vision to establish an Indigenous biorepository and research institute on Native American land led by Indigenous scientists,” Yracheta said. “Stanford’s help was pivotal to our success today.”

Michael Synder, Ph.D., chair of Stanford’s Department of Genetics, said, “This is a major milestone. NativeBio is the first repository fully owned and managed by Native Americans which is crucial given they are a sovereign nation. NativeBio has been at the forefront of state-of-the-art technologies for storing and maintaining biosamples and data. This award will enable them to continue to do so and serve as an important and central hub for Native American data.”

Although only 1% of university professors in the U.S. are Native American, almost half of the RADx Tribal Data Repository university teams are led by Indigenous faculty scientists including Krystal Tsosie, Ph.D. (Diné – Navajo) and Matt Anderson, Ph.D. (Eastern Band of Cherokee descent).

Dr. Tsosie is a NativeBio cofounder and assistant professor at Arizona State University. “We started NativeBio with a very simple premise, that research on Indigenous peoples’ samples should be led by Indigenous community members and Indigenous scientists. So, ‘for us, by us’ has been our motto,” Tsosie said. “Who is better than community members to drive researcher questions and to understand the data? Sometimes outsiders fail to understand other factors that contribute to disparities and health inequities outside the research samples.”

Matt Anderson, Ph.D., associate professor in medical genetics at the University of Wisconsin-Madison, said, “The RADx D4I initiative points to the need for tribal sovereign protection of Indigenous data that has been missing since the inception of federal scientific programs. Scientists are accountable to Indigenous people in the use of Tribal data, and NativeBio is accountable to Indian Country as being good stewards of their data. This approach models systems and understandings that more closely align with indigenous mechanisms of community responsibility. “

NativeBio Data is an Indigenous and independent 501 (C)(3) non-profit data repository and research institute founded in 2018 in Eagle Butte, South Dakota on the Cheyenne River Sioux Reservation. NativeBio is the first Indigenous genomic biorepository led by Natives and located in a sovereign American Indian Nation.

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